

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF *Ruellia tuberosa* TOPICAL HYDROGEL AGAINST SELECTED SKIN BACTERIAL AGENTS

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Abstract. This study aimed to formulate and evaluate a topical hydrogel incorporating *Ruellia tuberosa* extract for its antibacterial activity and wound-healing potential. The antibacterial efficacy of the plant extract was tested against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus vulgaris* using an in vitro disc diffusion assay. The most effective concentration, 750 mg/mL, demonstrated significant activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (mean zone of inhibition: 18.47 mm) and moderate activity against *Proteus vulgaris* (mean zone of inhibition: 11.37 mm), compared to mupirocin as a positive control. The optimized extract concentration was incorporated into a hydrogel base, which was then evaluated for its therapeutic potential, physical properties, and stability. The wound-healing assay, conducted using Sprague-Dawley rats, revealed that the *Ruellia tuberosa* hydrogel exhibited a comparable rate of wound reduction to mupirocin ointment, with the most significant decrease observed from Day 2 to Day 3. Stability testing showed that the hydrogel maintained its color, odor, and homogeneity over a week. These findings suggest that *Ruellia tuberosa* hydrogel holds promise as a natural alternative for treating bacterial skin infections and promoting wound healing. Further studies are recommended to enhance its bioavailability, expand its antimicrobial spectrum, and assess its long-term therapeutic effects.

Keywords: *Antibacterial, phytochemical, skin infections, therapeutic effects, wound healing assay*

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The vastness of nature and the increasing number of diseases necessitate the continual discovery and development of diseases and offer alternative treatments to the community. One of the present concerns is the prevalence of skin diseases. It has been observed that every year, the percentage of the global population suffering from skin diseases is 1.79%. These diseases have the potential to become extremely dangerous if they are not treated in their nascent stages. Skin diseases must be detected and diagnosed at the early stages so that serious risks to life are avoided (Sharma et al., 2023).

Throughout history and across different countries, people have relied on traditional healers, home remedies, and ancient medicinal knowledge to address their health and well-being needs. The World Health Organization's Global Report on Traditional and Complementary Medicine (2019) reveals the widespread use of various traditional medicine systems worldwide. These include acupuncture, herbal medicines, indigenous traditional medicine, homeopathy, traditional Chinese medicine, naturopathy, chiropractic, osteopathy, ayurvedic medicine, and Unani medicine. In fact, 170 WHO Member States have reported that their populations use traditional medicine. While traditional medicine is sometimes viewed as outdated and in need of replacement by modern science, what is often overlooked is its contribution to modern science and medicine. Traditional medicine has a long history of translating traditional products and practices into effective treatments for various health conditions. This highlights the ongoing relevance and value of traditional medicine in the context of modern healthcare.

The skin, the body's largest organ and the primary defense against harmful pathogens presents significant challenges in clinical practice due to the prevalence of skin diseases. These conditions not only impose a heavy burden on the healthcare system in terms of cost and utilization of resources, but they also pose a threat due to the emergence of drug-resistant organisms. The development of drug resistance presents a critical challenge in the management of various skin

diseases, particularly those necessitating secondary treatments such as chemotherapy. Multidrug-resistant organisms, including bacteria and other microorganisms, have developed resistance to antimicrobial drugs. This resistance undermines the effectiveness of treatment and exacerbates the severity of dermatologic diseases. One of the common examples of multidrug-resistant organisms is Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) (Shah & Safi, 2021).

The increasing resistance to antimicrobials (WHO, 2023) has prompted researchers to explore natural sources for treating diseases. *R. tuberosa* was selected as the plant of interest because of its promising potential as an antibacterial. While there is no guarantee that it will be effective against resistant microorganisms, there is hope it will surpass the activity of a control drug.

Statement of the Objectives

The study aimed to formulate a topical hydrogel from *R. tuberosa*'s crude extract and to assess its antibacterial activity against selected skin bacterial agents *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*.

Specifically, it aimed to:

1. Determine the antibacterial activity of *R. tuberosa* plant extract through in vitro assay using the following extract concentrations.
 - a) 250 mg/mL
 - b) 500 mg/mL
 - c) 750 mg/mL
2. Formulate a topical hydrogel of *R. tuberosa* plant extract using the most effective concentration;
3. Compare the wound healing potential of formulated topical hydrogel with mupirocin ointment;
4. Evaluate the formulated *R. tuberosa* topical hydrogel in terms of the following:
 - a) Physical properties
 - b) Stability

II. METHODOLOGY

This study used a comparative experimental design to determine the antibacterial potential of *R. tuberosa* plant extract through in vitro assays quantified through measurement of zones of inhibition. The most effective concentration of the extract was selected for formulation into a topical hydrogel. Subsequently, the formulated *R. tuberosa* topical hydrogel was compared with commercial mupirocin in a wound-healing assay.

The research was conducted at the Center for Natural Sciences at Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The CNS research laboratory was equipped with modern facilities and equipment necessary for the experimental procedures of the study. The university had an animal facility designed to house experimental animals, specifically Sprague-Dawley albino rats. The plant samples of *R. tuberosa* were collected from Purok Tabla, Salinas, Bambang Nueva Vizcaya. This location was known for the robust growth and abundance of the plant. Importantly, it was situated away from major roads, which minimized the risk of contamination that could have affected the integrity of the plant samples.

The experimental animals were Sprague-Dawley albino rats that were purchased from a local pet store in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The rats were identified and authenticated by the Provincial Veterinary Services Office. A veterinarian performed the identification and issued a certificate of identification for each experimental animal, verifying its breed and health status.

The collected *R. tuberosa* plants from Bambang were placed in a clean sack and brought directly to the Pharmacy laboratory for drying. The plants were washed with running water to remove the dirt and then with distilled water. They were placed on a tray for oven drying for at least 5 hours or until crispy dry. Dried *R. tuberosa* was powderized using an osteorizer or grinder.

The study used the approach introduced by Guevara (2005). Obtained *R. tuberosa* powder of 100 g was placed in an Erlenmeyer flask and macerated with 80% ethyl alcohol. The ethyl alcohol

added covered the whole *R. tuberosa* powder. The maceration lasted for 48 hours. The mixture was periodically stirred or shaken to facilitate the extraction of bioactive compounds from the plant material. The whole setup included covering the flask with aluminum foil.

After maceration, the mixture underwent filtration using cotton and cheesecloth. The whole mixture was poured through a funnel. The plant waste was discarded, and the liquid portion was subjected to evaporation using a water bath at 45 degrees Celsius to avoid excessive heat that could degrade the extract. The obtained crude extract was weighed, and three different concentrations were prepared to be used for the in vitro antibacterial assay. *R. tuberosa* plant extract was diluted with 95% ethanol in concentrations of 250 mg/mL, 500 mg/mL, and 750 mg/mL. The crude extract was weighed and placed in a test tube. Each prepared quantity of the extract, 250 mg, 500 mg, and 750 mg was added with 1 mL of 95% ethanol.

The antibacterial test was conducted following the protocol established by Guevara (2005). Initially, the microbial suspension was adjusted to match the turbidity standard of 0.5 McFarland. Subsequently, sterile filter paper discs were soaked in the extract for 24 hours. Mupirocin, at a concentration of 0.25 g/L, served as the positive control, while ethanol was utilized as the negative control. Prepared microbial suspensions of the two species, *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*, were streaked onto eight agar media plates, with four plates designated for each bacterium. In each plate, three filter paper discs were soaked in extracts of varying concentrations, representing three trials for each prepared concentration. Additionally, one disc was soaked in mupirocin (the positive control) for both *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*, and another disc was soaked in ethanol (the negative control) for each test organism.

Following the preparation, the Petri plates were incubated at a temperature of 37 °C for 24 hours. Four media plates were prepared for each microbial agent, with each plate containing three discs soaked in a plant extract tested against the respective microbial agent.

The formulation of hydrogel was adapted from Rescober et al. (2022) with modifications. The slight modification involved the replacement of one of the ingredients in the formulation with another that served the same purpose. Tragacanth was gradually dissolved in 20 mL of deionized water to prepare the hydrogel base. In comparison, gelatin was dissolved in 20 mL of hot deionized water. Once dissolved, the gelatin solution was gradually added to the Tragacanth solution and continuously stirred until it formed a homogeneous mixture. The ethanolic plant extracts of *R. tuberosa* were dissolved in 20 mL of deionized water and gradually added to the Tragacanth-gelatin solution, with continuous stirring throughout the process to ensure uniform mixing and prevent the formation of clumps or uneven distribution of components. A sufficient volume of solvent was added to the mixture to achieve the desired volume of 100 mL.

The formulated *R. tuberosa* hydrogel was characterized based on its visual and physical properties, including color, odor, and homogeneity. To assess its stability, the hydrogel was stored at 24 °C under controlled humidity of 53% and protected from direct light for one week. Stability was evaluated by observing any changes in phase separation, viscosity, and microbial contamination. The formulated *R. tuberosa* hydrogel, containing the concentration that showed the highest activity against *S. aureus*, was tested for its potential to heal wounds using the procedure outlined by Rescober et al. (2022). Sprague Dawley rats were acclimatized for 7 days prior to experimentation. Anesthesia was induced via intradermal injection of 0.1 mL/kg 2% Lidocaine to ensure the animals were insensible to pain during the procedure. Their back hair was shaved with a razor blade, and the surgical area was disinfected using 70% alcohol. The dorsal skin was folded and raised cranially and caudally at the midline to form a sandwich skinfold. Subsequently, the test animals were placed in a lateral position, and a 4-mm-diameter sterile biopsy punch was pressed down to completely remove the two skin layers and create a symmetrical, full-thickness excisional wound. Hemostasis in the wound area was achieved by blotting the wound with a cotton swab soaked in a normal saline solution. The rats were divided into three groups randomly: untreated (Group I), treated with *R. tuberosa* hydrogel (Group II), and treated with the standard drug Mupirocin ointment (Group III). The wounds were left exposed, and the rats were individually housed in cages thereafter (Rescober et al., 2022). Throughout the entire process of inflicting wounds on the test animals, researchers ensured that they were handled in the most humane

manner possible. Researchers confirmed that the injected anesthesia had served its purpose before inflicting the wound.

Wound size was measured on the 0th, 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, and 6th days using a Vernier caliper to ensure precise and consistent readings. The rate of wound healing was analyzed using the wound healing formula: Wound size at Present – Wound size in Previous Day. It is used to assess the progress of healing, reduce wound size, minimize scar tissue formation, lower infection risk, improve cosmetic outcomes, guide treatment decisions, and predict healing time, all of which are critical for effective wound management and optimal recovery.

Employing alternative water sources, such as hydrogels, became crucial if the rat-faced challenges in accessing a regular water source. Continuous monitoring was conducted, along with replacement fluids administered subcutaneously, intraperitoneally, or intravenously as directed by a veterinarian (CCAC, 2020).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Section 1. Antibacterial activity of *R. tuberosa* plant extract through in vitro assay

Table 1

Antibacterial Activity of R. Tuberosa Extract against Staphylococcus aureus and Proteus vulgaris Compared with Positive Control

Test Organism	Extract concentration (mg/mL)	Zone of inhibition (mm)				Inference
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Mean	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	250	13.93	15.51	17.77	15.74	Active
	500	16.67	16.94	18.63	17.41	Active
	750	17.50	18.10	19.82	18.47	Active
	Clindamycin (+ control)	24.08	25.90	26.77	25.58	Very active
	Ethanol (- control)	0	0	0	0	Inactive
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	250	8.53	9.88	13.24	10.55	Partially active
	500	9.88	10.25	11.35	10.49	Partially active
	750	10.16	10.79	13.17	11.37	Partially active
	Ciprofloxacin (+ control)	14.14	14.64	18.20	15.66	Active
	Ethanol (- control)	0	0	0	0	Inactive

Legend: < 10 mm: Inactive, 10-13 mm: Partially active, 14-19 mm: Active, 19 mm: Very active

The table presents the results of testing an extract against *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*, comparing the effectiveness of the extract with positive and negative controls. For *S. aureus*, the extract showed “active” results at 250, 500, and 750 mg/mL concentrations, with mean zones of inhibition ranging from 15.74 mm to 18.47 mm, while the positive control, Clindamycin, was “very active” with a mean zone of 25.58 mm. The negative control, ethanol, showed no inhibition (0 mm). For *P. vulgaris*, the extract showed “partially active” at all concentrations (250, 500, 750 mg/mL), with mean zones ranging from 10.49 mm to 11.37 mm. In contrast, the positive control, Ciprofloxacin, showed “active” results with a mean zone of 15.66 mm. Ethanol again showed no inhibition. These results indicate the extract is more effective against *S. aureus* than *P. vulgaris*, with both bacterial strains showing no response to ethanol.

According to Kader et al. (2012), *R. tuberosa* root extract exhibited significant antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and moderate activity against Gram-negative bacteria, supporting the current study’s findings of higher efficacy against *S. aureus*. The antibacterial activity of *R. tuberosa* can be linked to its phytochemical components, such as flavonoids, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds. These bioactive compounds have been shown to disrupt bacterial cell walls, inhibit

protein synthesis, and interfere with bacterial metabolism. A study by Chothani et al. (2024) further highlighted the presence of these compounds in *R. tuberosa*, emphasizing their role in its antibacterial properties.

The study demonstrates the antibacterial activity of *R. tuberosa* extract, particularly against *S. aureus*, suggesting its potential as a natural alternative or supplement to synthetic antibiotics. This is especially relevant given the growing concern over antibiotic resistance. The lower efficacy against *P. vulgaris* highlights the need for further research to enhance the extract’s activity against Gram-negative bacteria. This could focus on isolating and concentrating specific active compounds or exploring synergistic combinations with other antimicrobial agents.

Section 2. The Formulated Topical Hydrogel

The hydrogel was formulated using *R. tuberosa* crude extract at a concentration of 750 mg/mL as the active ingredient and primary source of therapeutic activity. Tragacanth (2% w/v) and gelatin (5% w/v) were incorporated as viscosity enhancers to improve the consistency of the formulation and reduce its watery texture. Distilled water served as the solvent and dispersion medium for all components, ensuring uniform distribution of the extract and stability of the hydrogel matrix.

Section 3. Wound Healing Potential of Hydrogel

Table 2

Wound Healing Process of R. tuberosa Hydrogel Using Sprague-Dawley Rat as Test Animal in Comparison with Mupirocin Ointment

Rat Group	Wound measurement (mm)	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Mean
Untreated	Size	3.22	3.03	2.62	1.73	0.70	0.54	2.26
	Reduction	0.78	0.19	0.41	0.89	1.03	0.16	0.57
<i>R. tuberosa</i> Hydrogel	Size	3.07	2.97	1.20	1.14	0.90	0.64	1.98
	Reduction	0.93	0.10	1.77	0.06	0.24	0.26	0.56
Mupirocin (positive control)	Size	2.84	2.67	1.07	0.87	0.77	0.50	1.81
	Reduction	1.16	0.17	1.60	0.20	0.10	0.27	0.58

The table presents a comparative analysis of the wound-healing effects of *R. tuberosa* hydrogel, mupirocin ointment, and an untreated control group in Sprague-Dawley rats. All groups began with an initial wound size of 4 mm on Day 0.

Figure 6
Bar Graph

The wound reduction results indicate varying effects of *R. tuberosa* hydrogel compared to the untreated and mupirocin-treated groups. On day one, all groups showed initial wound size reductions, with the hydrogel group yielding a value of 0.93, which was higher than the untreated group (0.78) but lower than the mupirocin-treated group (1.16). By day two, wound sizes significantly decreased across all groups, with the hydrogel group (0.10) exhibiting the least contraction compared to both the untreated (0.19) and mupirocin-treated (0.17) groups. On day three, wound reduction became more pronounced in the hydrogel (1.77) and mupirocin (1.60) groups, whereas the untreated group showed minimal improvement (0.41). On days four and five, the hydrogel-treated group continued to demonstrate reduced wound sizes. By Day 6, the untreated group exhibited the largest average wound size (2.26 mm), followed by the *R. tuberosa* hydrogel group (1.98 mm), and the mupirocin-treated group (1.81 mm). Among the groups, Mupirocin demonstrated the most consistent and effective wound-healing activity, with a total average wound size reduction of 0.27 mm over 6 days and a mean daily reduction of 0.58 mm. The *R. tuberosa* hydrogel group showed a total average reduction of 0.26 mm (mean: 0.56 mm), with the most significant reduction occurring early in the treatment period. The untreated group showed the slowest healing, with a total average reduction of 0.16 mm (mean: 0.57 mm). These results highlight the beneficial role of topical treatment in promoting wound healing. While *R. tuberosa* may fail to have the same efficacy in the reduction of wounds compared with mupirocin, the difference in its reduction capacity still implies a promising potential as an alternative natural wound healing agent.

The wound healing experiment anticipated several complications. One major concern was the psychological behavior of the rats, such as scratching, moving around, and licking their wounds, which could potentially interfere with the healing process. Additionally, the possibility of cross-contamination between rats was considered. To address these issues, each rat was placed in a personalized and clean enclosure to minimize such behaviors and prevent contamination.

Wound infection was also anticipated. However, the wounds did not exhibit any signs of inflammation, redness, or other physical indicators that would suggest infection. An unanticipated factor was the variation in wound depth. This difference appeared to influence both the rate of wound healing and the likelihood of scarring. Deeper wounds generally require more blood vessel formation and tend to heal more slowly due to prolonged inflammation, as observed in full-thickness wounds (Eming et al., 2014). In contrast, superficial wounds heal primarily through re-epithelialization. Partial-thickness wounds, which extend from the epidermis into the dermis, involve a more complex repair process than superficial wounds, which affect only the epidermis. Full-thickness wounds, reaching into the dermis and subcutaneous tissue, require extended healing time due to the depth of tissue damage (Gurtner et al., 2008).

Section 4. Characteristics of the formulated *R. tuberosa*

Table 3

Physical Properties and Stability of the Hydrogel

	Physical properties		Stability	
	After formulation		After one week	
Color	Dark green	Opaque appearance with a dark green color, indicative of the presence of the plant extract. The color was uniform throughout the hydrogel, suggesting a well-	Dark green	The color remained consistent, retaining its dark green hue, which suggested stability in the formulation.

Physical properties		Stability		
Odor	Mild	mixed formulation. The odor was mild and characteristic of the <i>R. tuberosa</i> plant, which is typically earthy and herbal. This pleasant aroma was not overpowering, making it suitable for topical applications.	Somewhat stronger or more noticeable than before	The odor persisted, although it became slightly more pronounced, reflecting the gradual release of volatile compounds from the hydrogel matrix. This change in odor could enhance the sensory experience during application.
After formulation		After one week		
Homogeneity	No visible clumps	Homogeneity was confirmed through visual inspection, as there were no visible clumps or separations in the gel matrix, indicating that the components were evenly distributed.	No signs of phase separation or sedimentation	The homogeneity of the hydrogel continued to be satisfactory, with no signs of phase separation or sedimentation, indicating that the formulation maintained its structural integrity over the week.

The results show that the *R. tuberosa* hydrogel formulation has remained stable for a week. The hydrogel exhibited a consistent dark green color throughout the observation period. No changes in hue, discoloration, or color loss were observed, which suggests that the formulation did not undergo significant chemical degradation, affecting its color and stability. The hydrogel had a mild grassy or green scent, which became more pronounced over the week. While the odor intensified, it did not develop a rancid or foul smell that could indicate instability. The stronger scent likely reflects the gradual release of volatile compounds from the *R. tuberosa* extract, indicating the presence of active components in the formulation. The hydrogel remained physically stable, showing no signs of clumping, phase separation, or sedimentation. This consistency ensures the even distribution of active ingredients, which is crucial for its application and effectiveness. Overall, the *R. tuberosa* hydrogel formulation demonstrated good stability over the week. Its color and homogeneity remained unchanged, while the odor became stronger but did not indicate spoilage. The observed changes suggest the sustained presence of active components, increasing the formulation's stability.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The study successfully achieved its primary objective by demonstrating that *Ruellia tuberosa* extract can be effectively formulated into a topical hydrogel with significant antibacterial and wound-healing properties. The 750 mg/mL concentration exhibited the highest antibacterial

activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus vulgaris*, and the resulting hydrogel formulation showed comparable wound-healing potential to the standard mupirocin treatment. Therefore, the formulated *R. tuberosa* plant hydrogel represents a natural alternative for wound management, combining both antibacterial and wound-healing properties in a single formulation. This study highlights the potential of natural products in developing effective therapies for skin infections and wound healing, encouraging further research into the optimization and clinical application of *R. tuberosa*-based formulations.

Recommendations

1. To assess the hydrogel's safety, efficacy, and mechanisms of action in clinical settings.
2. To consider other hydrogel components to compare the wound-healing properties of *Ruellia tuberosa* extract when formulated with a different hydrogel base.
3. To investigate the incorporation of stabilizers or enhancers to extend shelf life and maintain formulation consistency.
4. To evaluate the extract's antibacterial activity against a broader range of pathogens to determine its full antimicrobial spectrum.
5. To conduct longer-term studies with larger sample sizes to assess its sustained wound-healing effects and overall safety.

References

- Abdi, G., Jain, M., Patil, N., Tariq, M., Choudhary, S., Kumar, P., Raj, N. S., Ali, S. S. M., & Uthappa, U. T. (2024). Tragacanth gum-based hydrogels for drug delivery and tissue engineering applications. *Frontiers in Materials*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmats.2024.1296399>
- Allen-Worthington, K. H., Brice, A. K., Marx, J. O., & Hankenson, F. C. (2015). Intraperitoneal injection of ethanol for the euthanasia of laboratory mice (*Mus musculus*) and rats (*Rattus norvegicus*). *Journal of the American Association for Laboratory Animal Science: JAALAS*, 54(6), 769-778. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26632787/>
- Arirudran, B., Sarawathy, A., & Krishnamurthy, V. (2011, July). Antimicrobial activity of *Ruellia tuberosa* L. (Whole Plant). *Pharmacognosy Journal*. 3(23). <https://doi.org/10.5530/pj.2011.23.14>
- Arya, N. R., & Rafiq, N. B. (2023, May 29). Candidiasis. *StatPearls - NCBI Bookshelf*. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK560624/>
- Barit, J. J. G., Abalos-Babaran, S., Obbus, S. F. V., & Dofitas, B. L. (2021). The clinical profile, wound dressings, and clinical outcomes of in-patients with pressure ulcers at a tertiary hospital in the Philippines: A seven-year retrospective study. *Acta Medica Philippina/Acta Medica Philippina*, 55(5). <https://doi.org/10.47895/amp.v55i5.2767>
- Brower, M., Grace, M., Kotz, C. M., & Koya, V. (2015). Comparative analysis of growth characteristics of Sprague Dawley rats obtained from different sources. *Animal Research Laboratory*, 31(4) 166-173. <https://doi.org/10.5625/lar.2015.31.4.166>
- Brown, C. J., DVM, & Donnelly, T. M., DVM. (2004). Rodent husbandry and care. *Veterinary Clinics of North America: Exotic Animal Practice*. 7(2). 201-225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evex.2004.02.005>

- Bush, L. M. (2023, March 10). Streptococcal infections. *MSD Manual Consumer Version*. <https://www.msmanuals.com/home/infections/bacterial-infections-gram-positive-bacteria/streptococcal-infections>
- Canadian Council on Animal Care (2003) *Canadian Council on Animal Care guidelines on laboratory animal facilities — characteristics, design and development*. <https://ccac.ca/Documents/Standards/Guidelines/Facilities.pdf>
- Chen, L., Mirza, R., Kwon, Y., DiPietro, L. A., & Koh, T. J. (2015). The murine excisional wound model: Contraction revisited. *Wound Repair and Regeneration*, 23(6), 874–877. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wrr.12335>
- Chothani, D. L., Patel, M., Mishra, S., & Vaghasiya H. (2024). Review on *Ruellia tuberosa* (Cracker plant). <https://cabidigitalibrary.org.by222.127.40.70>
- Clarkson, J. M., Martin, J. L., & McKeegan, D. E. F. (2022). A review of methods used to kill laboratory rodents: issues and opportunities. *Laboratory Animals*, 56(5), 419- 436. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00236772221097472>
- Cunha, B. A. (2023). *Proteus infections*. Medscape. <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/226434-overview>
- Dall, C. (October 14, 2023). Mupirocin outperforms nasal antiseptics against Staph infections. *Center for Infectious Disease Research and Policy*. <https://www.cidrap.umn.edu/antimicrobial-stewardship/mupirocin-outperforms-nasal-antiseptic-against-staph-infections>
- Eming, S. A., Martin, P., & Tomic-Canic, M. (2014). Wound repair and regeneration: Mechanisms, signaling, and translation. *Science Translational Medicine*, 6(265), 265sr6. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scitranslmed.3009337>
- Erwin, D. Z., & Chen, P. (2024, January 11). Mupirocin. *StatPearls - NCBI Bookshelf*. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK599499>
- Galef, B. G. (2010). *Norway Rats*. Elsevier Ltd. In *Elsevier eBooks* 573-578. <https://doi.org/10.1016/6978-0-08-045337-8.00046-2>
- Gangwar, A., Kumar, P., Singh, R., & Kush, P. (2021). Recent advances in mupirocin delivery strategies for the treatment of bacterial skin and soft tissue infection. *Future Pharmacology*, 1(1), 80–103. <https://doi.org/10.3390/futurepharmacol1010007>
- Gokulakrishnan, S., Dharanya, M., & Ilango, K. B. (2023). Standardization and solvent comparative study of *Ruellia tuberosa* L. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 12(9). WJPR - abstract. https://www.wjpr.net/abstract_show/22273
- Guevara, B. Q. & UST Research Center for the Natural Sciences. (2005). *A Guidebook to Plant Screening: Phytochemical and Biological* (Revised Edition). University of Santo Tomas PUBLISHING HOUSE, Manila.
- Gurtner, G. C., Werner, S., Barrandon, Y., & Longaker, M. T. (2008). Wound repair and regeneration. *Nature*, 453(7193), 314–321. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature07039>

- Haque, R., Song, A. D., Lee, J., Lee, S. V., & Suh, J. M. (2025). Essential resources and best practices for laboratory mouse research. *Molecules and Cells*, 48(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mocell.2025.100178>
- James Cook University (n.d.), Humane killing of animals guidelines, https://www.jcu.edu.au/data/assets/pdf_file/0016/310219/Humane-Killing-of-Animals-Guideline.pdf
- Kader, A., Parvin, S., Chowduri, A. U., & Haque, E. (2012). Antibacterial, antifungal and insecticidal activities of ruellia tuberosa (L.) Root Extract. *J. bio-sci.* 20, 91-97. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Aktar-Chouduri/publication/260423186_Antibacterial_antifungal_and_insecticidal_activities_of_Ruellia_tuberosa_L_root_extract/links/0f3175312ca1a6a8e6000000/Antibacterial-antifungal-and-insecticidal-activities-of-Ruellia-tuberosa-L-root-extract.pdf
- Kapusta, O., Jarosz, A., Stadnik, K., Giannakoudakis, D. A., Barczyński, B., & Barczak, M. (2023, February). Antimicrobial natural hydrogels in biomedicine: Properties, applications, and challenges—A concise review. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 24(3), 2191. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9917233/>
- Kindi, A. A., Alkahtani, A. M., Nalubega, M., El-Chami, C., O'Neill, C., Arkwright, P. D., & Pennock, J. L. (2019, September 24). Staphylococcus aureus internalized by skin keratinocytes evade antibiotic killing. *Front. Microbiol.* (10), 2242. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.02242>
- Leonard, J. (2024, July 8). *How to recognize and treat an infected wound*. <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/325040#:~:text=If%20bacteria%20or%20other%20pathogens%20enter%20a%20wound%2C%20an%20infection%20can%20occur>
- Narayanaswamy, R., & Torchilin, V. P. (2019). Hydrogels and their applications in targeted drug delivery. *Molecules/Molecules Online/Molecules Annual*, 24(3), 603. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24030603>
- Neosporin. (n.d). *Minor infected wounds*. <https://www.neosporin.com/first-aid-info/>
- Patil P. B., Datir S. K., Saudagar R. B. (2019). Review on topical gels as drug delivery system. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*. 9(3-s), 989-994. <https://www.jddtonline.info/index.php/jddt/article/view/2930/2302>
- Qureshi, S. (March 03, 2023). Pseudomonas aeruginosa Infection. *Medscape*. <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/226748-overview>
- Rescober, A. A. S., Blanco, I. F. M., Janio, J. A. T., Custodio, S. E. A., Daguman, F. L., Viray, J. M. D., & Dollesin, J. H. (2022). Antimicrobial and wound healing activity of ixora coccinea leaf extract in a hydrogel formulation. *Acta Medica Philippina*. 56(7).
- Rodrigues, A. B., Silva, C. S. O., Rocha, M. R., Santos, R. O., & Torres, G. V. (2016). Effects of low-level laser therapy on the healing of skin wounds in rats. *Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da USP*, 50(6), 963-969. <https://www.scielo.br/j/reeusp/a/PJQVpjGdzPmpLShrvptrVcc>
- Rubio-Canalejas, A., Baelo, A., Herbera, S., Blanco-Cabra, N., Vukomanovic, M., & Torrents, E. (2022). 3D spatial organization and improved antibiotic treatment of a Pseudomonas aeruginosa-

- Staphylococcus aureus wound biofilm by nanoparticle enzyme delivery. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.959156>
- Rüther, L., & Voss, W. (2021). Hydrogel or Ointment? Comparison of five different galenics regarding tissue breathability and transepidermal water loss. *Heliyon*, 7(1), e06071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06071>
- Sander, J. E. (2022, September 21). Disposal of carcasses and disinfection of premises-clinical pathology and procedures. *MSD Veterinary Manual* <https://www.msddvetmanual.com/clinical-pathology-and-procedures/disposal-of-carcasses-and-disinfection-of-premises/disposal-of-carcasses-and-disinfection-of-premises>
- Sharma M., Jain B., Kargeti C., Gupta V., & Gupta D. (2023). Detection and Diagnosis of Skin Diseases Using Residual Neural Networks (RESNET). *International Journal of Image and Graphics*, 21(5), 2140002. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219467821400027>
- Shah, H., & Safi, S. Z. (2021). Drug resistance in skin diseases. In *Springer eBooks*, 197–234. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-76320-6_7
- Singhal, H. & Kaur K. (2023, March 16). Wound infection: Background, pathophysiology, etiology. *Medscape*. <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/188988-overview?form=fpf>
- Statista. (2024). Wound Care - Philippines | Statista market forecast. <https://www.statista.com/outlook/hmo/otc-pharmaceuticals/wound-care/phiippines>
- Stuart, G. U. (2024). *Philippine medicinal plants*. <http://stuartxchange.org/Ruellia>
- Sudakov, S.K., et. al. (2021). Age-related individual behavioral characteristics of adult wistar rats. *Animals, Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute*, 11, 2282. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani1082282>
- Talapko, J., Juzbasic, M., Matijevic, T., Pustijanac, E., Bekic, S., Kortis, I., & Skrlec, I. (2021, January 22). *Candida albicans* - The virulence factors and clinical manifestations of infection. *PubMed Central*. 7(2), 29. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7912069/>
- Taylor, T. A. & Unakal, C. G. (2023, July 17). *Staphylococcus aureus* Infection. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28722898/>
- Tang, Y., Xu, H., Wang, X., Dong, S., Guo, L., Zhang, S., Yang, X., Liu, C., Jiang, X., Kan, M., Zhang, J., & Xu, C. (2023, August 26). Advances in preparation and application of antibacterial hydrogels. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*, 21, 300. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12951-023-02025-8>
- The University of Texas (2020). Guidelines for the use of cervical dislocation for rodent euthanasia. *The University of Texas*. [https://research.utexas.edu/wpcontent/uploads/sites/3/2022/03/GUIDELINE_04-Use of Cervical Dislocation for Rodent Euthanasia_2020_1207 nl.pdf](https://research.utexas.edu/wpcontent/uploads/sites/3/2022/03/GUIDELINE_04-Use_of_Cervical_Dislocation_for_Rodent_Euthanasia_2020_1207_nl.pdf)
- The Wound Pros (2024). *Wound Infections - Symptoms, diagnosis, and treatment*. <https://www.thewoundpros.com/post/infected-chronic-wounds-symptoms-diagnosis-and-treatment>

- Universe84a. (n.d.). Proteus vulgaris- Introduction, morphology, pathogenicity, lab diagnosis, treatment, prevention, and keynotes. *Universe84a*. <https://universe84a.com/proteus-vulgaris-introduction-2/>
- Vyas, J. M. (2022, December 4). Candida infection of the skin. *UF Health*. <https://ufhealth.org/conditions-and-treatments/candida-infection-of-the-skin>
- World Health Organization. (2023, August 10). *Traditional medicine has a long history of contributing to conventional medicine and continues to hold promise*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/feature-stories/detail/traditional-medicine-has-a-long-history-of-contributing-to-conventional-medicine-and-continues-to-hold-promise>
- Wanat, K. A., & Norton, S. A. (2024). Dermatologic Conditions. *CDC Yellow Book 2024*. <https://wwwnc.cdc.gov/travel/yellowbook/2024/posttravel-evaluation/dermatologic-conditions>
- Yazdi, M. T., Nazarnezhad, S., Mousavi, S., Amiri, M. S., Darroudi, M., Bairo, F., & Kargozar, S. (2021). Gum Tragacanth (GT): A versatile biocompatible material beyond borders. *Molecules*, 26(6), 1510. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26061510>
- Zhang, L., Wang, Y., Yang, M., Yu, W., Zhao, Z., & Liu, Y. (2024). An injectable, self-healing, adhesive multifunctional hydrogel promotes bacteria-infected wound healing. *Polymers*, 16(10), 1316. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16101316>